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PARTNERS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 792210.

GEOFIT Project

Cost-effective enhanced geothermal systems for energy efficient building retrofitting

Project ID: 792210

Project start: May 2018

Duration: 4 years

In Europe, the building sector is responsible for the 40% of the total energy consumption and represents about a third of Europe's CO₂ emissions'. **Heating and cooling accounts for 50% of this EU annual energy consumption.** This is a huge socio-economic and environmental problem, more if we consider that almost half of the EU buildings have boilers installed before 1992, with an efficiency rate of below 60%¹. For this reason, key drivers of the EU building market are the EU climate and energy package, adopted in 2008, altogether with the well-known EU "20-20-20" targets.

Although energy renovation of existing buildings could help to achieve those "20-20-20" targets, the refurbishment rate is currently below 1% and renewables are not widely used in the building sector. Indeed, in 2015, renewable energy accounted for only 18.6% of total energy use for heating and cooling in the EU-28. Albeit, a gradual shift over the last five years is observed from fossil fuels to renewable energy. By means of Directives, Recommendations and Regulations, the European Commission is giving a direction to the future of sustainable energy use and supporting the Low Carbon Energy in Buildings. In this context, **Shallow Geothermal Energy represents a renewable energy source with a large potential of energy savings and greenhouse gas emissions reduction in the building sector to achieve all major objectives of the EU's energy policy.** Moreover main reference organisations - such as ECTP² and RHC³ - have effectively promoted and road-mapped the cost-effective integration of renewable energy sources (RES) into building technical systems, considering the development of effective and affordable enhanced geothermal systems (EGSs) crucial to exploit the EU geothermal potential as major source of energy supply for heating and cooling purposes, by targeting the bottlenecks that hinder full deployment of geothermal systems as one of the key concepts in energy efficient building retrofitting.

¹ European Commission: "Towards a smart, efficient and sustainable heating and cooling sector", Brussels, 16 February 2016.

² <http://e2b.ectp.org/>

³ http://www.rhc-platform.org/fileadmin/Publications/Geothermal_SRA.pdf

GEOFIT will therefore answer to this challenge as an integrated industrially driven action aimed at deployment of cost effective enhanced geothermal systems (EGS) on energy efficient building retrofitting. This entails the development technical development of innovative EGS and its components, namely, non-standard heat exchanger configurations, a novel hybrid heat pump and electrically driven compression heat pump systems and suite of heating and cooling components to be integrated with the novel GSHP concepts, all specially designed to applied in energy efficient retrofitting projects. To make viable the novel enhanced geothermal systems in energy efficient building retrofitting, a suite of tools and technologies is developed, including: low invasive risk assessment technologies, site-inspection and work-site building monitoring techniques (SHM), control systems for cost-effective and optimized EGS in operation phase and novel BIM-enabled dedicated tools for management of geothermal based retrofitting works (GEOBIM platform). Furthermore, the project is committed with the application of novel drilling techniques as the improved low invasive vertical drilling and trenchless technologies.

SHALLOW-EARTH HEAT EXCHANGER CONCEPTS COUPLED TO INNOVATIVE DRILLING TECHNIQUES

Images from partner Uponor and partner Catalana De Perforacions

GEOFIT brings these technical developments within a new management framework based on Integrated Design and Delivery Solutions for the geothermal based retrofitting process. The IDDS driven process will materialise in the Geo-BIM enabled Retrofitting Management Platform (Geo-BIM tool). By using the 5 demonstration sites as open case studies in 4 countries and climates, featuring different representative technical scenarios/business models, GEOFIT will leverage its key exploitable results, adapted business models and market oriented dissemination for maximizing impact and wide adoption of these novel geothermal technologies and approaches.

(OPEN) PILOTS

4 Countries, 5 Building Types, Different Soil Conditions, 3 Different Climates

For more details on the objectives of GEOFIT, please consult this page:
<http://geofit-project.eu/project/objectives/>

The GEOFIT consortium includes experts from:

Website: www.geofit-project.eu
Contact: info@geofit-project.eu
Twitter: twitter.com/EuGeofit
LinkedIn: linkedin.com/company/geofit-project

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GEOFIT Project abstract

Project ID: 792210

Funded under: H2020-EU.3.3.2. - Low-cost, low-carbon energy supply

Deployment of novel GEOthermal systems, technologies and tools for energy efficient building retroFITting.

From 2018-05-01 to 2022-04-30

Project details

Total cost: EUR 9 861 980

EU contribution: EUR 7 896 940,14

Coordinated in: Italy

Topic(s): LCE-17-2017 - Easier to install and more efficient geothermal systems for retrofitting buildings

Call for proposal: H2020-LCE-2017-RES-IA

Funding scheme: IA - Innovation action

Objective

GEOFIT is an integrated industrially driven action aimed at deployment of cost effective enhanced geothermal systems (EGS) on energy efficient building retrofitting. This entails the development technical development of innovative EGS and its components, namely, non-standard heat exchanger configurations, a novel hybrid heat pump and electrically driven compression heat pump systems and suite of heating and cooling components to be integrated with the novel GSHP concepts, all specially designed to applied in energy efficient retrofitting projects. To make viable the novel EGS in energy efficient building retrofitting, a suite of tools and technologies is developed, including: low invasive risk assessment technologies, site-inspection and worksite building monitoring techniques (SHM), control systems for cost-effective and optimized EGS in operation phase and novel BIM-enabled dedicated tools for management of geothermal based retrofitting works (GEOBIM platform). Furthermore, the project is committed with the application of novel drilling techniques as the improved low invasive vertical drilling and trenchless technologies.

GEOFIT brings these technical developments within a new management framework based on Integrated Design and Delivery Solutions for the geothermal based retrofitting process. The IDDS driven process will materialise in the Geo-BIM enabled Retrofitting Management Platform (Geo-BIM tool). By using the 5 demonstration sites as open case studies in 4 countries and climates, featuring different representative technical scenarios/business models, GEOFIT will leverage its key exploitable results, adapted business models and market oriented dissemination for maximizing impact and wide adoption of these novel geothermal technologies and approaches.

Link: https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/215047_en.html

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GEOFIT Call

Call topic: LCE17- Easier to install and more efficient geothermal systems for retrofitting buildings

Call for proposals: Competitive Low-Carbon Energy (H2020-LCE-2017-RES-IA)

Topic description:

Specific Challenge:

The cost and efficiency of existing geothermal systems, mostly based on vertical wells, to provide heating and cooling in buildings being retrofitted or renovated are not very competitive in particular when digging is difficult. The challenge is to demonstrate the cost-effectiveness and efficiency of geothermal systems for heating and cooling in individual installations being retrofitted. Scope:

Proposals shall target easy to install and efficient underground coupling systems for retrofitting existing types of buildings or adaptable to existing types of buildings, including historical buildings, to make geothermal energy a standard source of heat and cold in building renovation. The difficulties in drilling in built environments must be taken into consideration and properly addressed. Proposals might address the need for improved and more cost-efficient heat pumps to optimize the use of the energy generated by the proposed geothermal system. Synergies may be considered with activities initiated under the Energy Efficiency call topics EE-10-2016 and EE-11-2016.

TRL 7 shall be achieved at the end of the project (please see part G of the General Annexes).

This topic will contribute to the PPP on Energy-efficient Buildings.

Opening the project's test sites, pilot and demonstration facilities, or research infrastructures for practice oriented education, training or knowledge exchange is encouraged.

The Commission considers that proposals requesting a contribution from the EU of between EUR 5 to 8 million would allow this specific challenge to be addressed appropriately. Nonetheless, this does not preclude submission and selection of proposals requesting other amounts.

Expected Impact:

The action will result in the demonstration of geothermal systems, to be used in existing buildings, that make geothermal energy a viable and cost-competitive source of energy for heating and cooling. The demonstrated systems will be easy to install in built environments and have a proved efficiency in different geological conditions. The action will increase the commercial attractiveness of geothermal energy for heating and cooling and therefore increase the penetration of this renewable energy source.

Link: <http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/opportunities/h2020/topics/lce-17-2017.html>

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GEOFIT Project Images

GEOFIT Kick-off meeting with its 24 partners

R2M Solution's drone used for structural building monitoring in Perugia (Italy)

R2M Solution's experts driving the drone in Perugia (Italy)

The pilot building in Perugia (Italy)

Cloud point reconstruction of the Perugia pilot building based on pictures taken with the drone

Cloud point reconstruction of the Perugia pilot building based on pictures taken with the drone

Ground survey in the pilot site of Sant Cugat

Georadar and GPS used during the ground survey in the pilot site of Sant Cugat

